

European Public Local Authorities' Network for
driving the Energy Transition

D5.3 - National Webinars' recordings and reports

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Executive Summary

ePLANET project is a Coordination and Support Action cofounded by the European Commission through the Horizon 2020 program. ePLANET aims to deploy a new clustering governance for an energy transition based on a digital framework to share harmonised information, facilitating the adoption of coordinated energy transition actions by the European public sector.

This document (deliverable 5.3 “National Webinars’ recordings and reports”) provides an overview of the recordings and reports organised with the three pilot regions of the project, along with key takeaways. It also includes a general description of the scale-up programme with timelines for each region and an introduction to the reporting template.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

ABBREVIATION OR ACRONYM	DESCRIPTION
CoMo-Europe	Covenant of Mayors Europe
DDGI	Diputació de Girona
EAZK	Energy Agency of the Zlín Region
EE	Energy Efficiency
EPC	Energy Performance Contracting
RES	Renewable Energy Solutions
UC	Use Case
WP	Work Package

1 Overview of the Scale-Up activities

In this section, you will first find an overview of the scale-up programme, which includes the National Webinars, with a description of their link with other ePLANET Work Packages (WP) and activities. In the second section, you will find a timeline of all scale-up programmes planned for each pilot region.

1.1 Scale-up at the national level and within pilot regions

The first section is a general description of the scale-up activities, followed by explanations of their connection with capacity-building activities to be carried out in the WP4.

1.1.1 General description

The scale-up activities are part of Task 5.2 - Scale-up at national level and within pilot regions. The main purpose of this task is to transfer the ePLANET methodology and platform using the training material developed in Work Package 4 (WP4). The way forward was described in the Replication and Networking plan (D5.1) developed at the beginning of the project in January 2022. This plan has a section dedicated to scale-up activities at national and within the regions of ePLANET pilot sites.

The overall aim of these activities was to include more public authorities in the project. Each pilot site partner organised 2 national webinars and 1 workshop. They were also in charge of reaching out to the target audience in their country and region, focusing on authorities who had not been actively engaged in the project so far.

The activities we will focus on in this deliverable are:

- 6 scale up public webinars to showcase the platform, disseminate the project outcomes and for peer mentoring between public authorities to build up capacity on national level.

The specific agenda of each activity has been defined within the pilot region, taking the local needs and circumstances into account. Most of the webinars have been recorded and made available online on the ePLANET website, YouTube channel, and project partners' websites to engage further municipalities that could not participate on the day.

Each activity has been summarised within the ePLANET report template to document the findings and lessons learned for other partners in English.

1.1.2 Connection with the capacity-building activities (WP4)

As planned in the Grant Agreement and the Networking and Replication plan (D5.1), the scale-up activities were built on the training material developed in WP4 on User Empowerment. The Capacity Building Programme in WP4 consists of a total of 24 activities to be implemented between M20 and M31. Each pilot territory benefited from 8 activities, targeting stakeholders at the pilot territory level. Similarly, the Scale-Up Program in WP5 includes a total of 9 activities to be implemented between M20 and M36. These activities involve stakeholders not only at the pilot level but also at the national level.

To avoid stakeholder fatigue and ensure meaningful participation in the project's impact, we have collaborated with each pilot owner to identify the two most promising activities from WP4 that could be of interest to stakeholders at the national level.

You can find the identified activities per region in the next section. These activities have been collaboratively organised, ensuring that the content is tailored to address the national-level stakeholders' interests and requirements. For some activities, an opportunity to organise them in person arose and was seized to enhance further their reach.

1.2 Timeline per region

Below are the timelines gathering all the scale-up activities planned for each pilot partner. The **purple activities** correspond to collaborative activities with WP4 capacity-building and the **orange activities** are activities solely dedicated to a scale-up objective.

1.2.1 Zlín pilot

1.2.2 Girona pilot

1.2.3 Crete pilot

2 Reporting of the activities

This section is dedicated to reporting each pilot partner's scale-up activities. In the first section, we describe the reporting methodology chosen, followed by three subsections describing each pilot region's activities.

2.1 Template report

It was decided to use a single report template for capacity-building activities and scale-up activities to facilitate the reporting process for the project partner in charge. It also avoids duplication of reporting of the collaborative activities (capacity-building and scale-up).

You can find the template report in the annexes (3.1 Template report). It consists of a table with 13 rows and two columns, one for the instructions and the other one to be completed by the partner in charge. The first three rows are about the event type (webinar or workshop), the event title and the event date. The next row asks about the partner in charge and the speaker's name who presented the ePLANET results. Then, we have two practical sections on the event's location and the language in which it was held. We then added a box to report on the number and type of participants. It is followed by a box to write a short description of the event. After that comes a section to specify the ePLANET content presented. This section is open but we provide the following suggestions: Showcase of the ePLANET platform; Presentation of governance concepts; Invitation to next Stakeholder Forums; Best practices; Local energy community; Promotion of MoU. The two next boxes are to put a link to relevant material such as the presentation, the agenda, pictures, the participants list and the recording if applicable. The penultimate row is dedicated to key takeaways or learnings which can be useful to take into account for next scale-up/capacity-building activity or that could be relevant for any other ePLANET activity. We suggest to share 3 takeaways/learnings. The last row is a free space to give additional remarks if applicable. After the table we included a link to the folder where the report and all relevant material should be uploaded. Just before the table we added a reminder that the report should be returned at the latest 7 working days after the event.

Recordings are not available for all the activities for different reasons, all of which are specified in each report completed by the pilot partner.

2.2 Zlín activities

2.2.1 Activity 1: First meeting of the interregional energy platform of the Czech Republic

The Energy Agency of the Zlín Region (EAZK) completed its first scale-up activity in Brno on November 9th, 2023. The director of EAZK, Miroslava Knotková, took part in the first meeting of the newly established "Interregional energy platform of regions of the Czech Republic" which aims to define and cooperate in the most urgent issues in energy common for all regions in the Czech Republic.

EAZK took an active part in this meeting and introduced the clustering governance concept developed within ePLANET project. This concept identifies opportunities for regions to play a more active role in ongoing energy transition. As an example, it was introduced to the audience

how to cope with challenges on regional issues related to governance facilitation and data management. The newly developed ePLANET platform and particularly the Use Case 2 on the performance of public building stock was also presented. For more information, you can find the agenda of the event and the PowerPoint presentation used to introduce ePLANET results in the annexes (3.2.1 Activity 1).

This activity was organised in a workshop format and gathered 29 participants from all 14 NUTS Regions of the Czech Republic, represented by stakeholders from regional authorities or regional energy agencies. Five energy facilities from different parts of the Czech Republic were also present. For practical reasons, as the activity was held in an in-person format, only pictures of the event are available, but no recordings were made.

Figure 2-1 - EAZK director introduction at the Interregional energy platform of the Czech Republic

Figure 2-2 - Presentation of ePLANET results

Figure 2-3 - Presentation of the clustering governance concept

2.2.2 Activity 2: Second meeting of the interregional energy platform of the Czech Republic

The Energy Agency of the Zlín Region (EAZK) completed its second scale-up activity in Hradec Králové on January 11th, 2024. Jan Vidomus, project manager from EAZK, took part in the second meeting of the newly established “Interregional energy platform of regions of the Czech Republic” which aims to define and cooperate in the most urgent issues in energy common for all regions in the Czech Republic.

The agenda of the meeting was focused on exchange of experience in construction of intelligent buildings, installation of Renewable Energy Solutions (RES), concept/strategy of individual regions, installation of charging stations, participation in the preparation of regional investments, application to energy.

EAZK took an active part in this meeting and introduced the approach of the Zlín Region to the project development and financing with reference to the ePLANET platform as a new integral part of decision-making process. Available financing sources were introduced with the special focus on national programmes such as OP Environment, NP Environment or Modernisation Fund. Alternative financing methods, such as Energy Performance Contracting (EPC), citizen cooperatives etc. were also mentioned. However, in the current situation, when national sources are available, they put in the shade other ways of financing Energy Efficiency (EE) and Renewable Energy Solutions (RES).

For more information, you can find the event's agenda and the PowerPoint presentation used to introduce ePLANET results in the annexes (3.2.2 Activity 2).

This activity was organised in a workshop format and gathered 17 participants from 9 NUTS regions of the Czech Republic, represented by stakeholders from regional authorities or regional energy agencies. For practical reasons, as the activity was held in an in-person format, only pictures of the event are available, but no recordings were made.

Figure 2-4 Second meeting of the interregional energy platform of the Czech Republic

Figure 2-5 Second meeting of the interregional energy platform of the Czech Republic

2.2.3 Key takeaways and learnings from Zlín national webinars

- The newly established interregional platform will share its views on the current energy situation in the Czech Republic and the EU. Among the topics and experiences that will be shared will be, for example, the combined purchase of energy on the PXE exchange, digitalisation of the data collection and management process, the new state energy concept, inter-regional coordination in the field of energy management, etc.
- Given the circumstances with funds available on the national level, it is important for all regions to utilise those funds in the most effective ways possible. Meetings on experience exchange, such as the interregional energy platform, are an important way to share information and best practices. On the other hand, the other ways of alternative innovative financing (EPC, municipal green bonds, citizen cooperatives, revolving loan funds etc.) must be taken into consideration in order to develop a functional, sustainable, and safe portfolio of financing for the public sector for EE and RES projects.

2.3 Girona activities

2.3.1 Activity 1: Creating local energy communities in industrial environments

The regional council of Girona (DDGI) organised its first scale-up activity in collaboration with LIMA in a webinar format, which was held in Catalan on the 27th of February 2024. Olga Barranchina, an expert from LIMA, moderated the event and gave a general introduction to the ePLANET project.

The agenda of the meeting was focused on energy communities in industrial environments, acknowledging them as key tools for decentralising and democratising the energy sector. In Girona, the first initiatives focused on empowering citizens and local administrations to take control of their energy needs, fostering greater community involvement and decision-making. However, industries also play a crucial role in this transition, contributing to the overall sustainability and efficiency of the energy landscape. This webinar delved into the potential

for shared self-consumption of renewable energies within industrial areas, examining how collective efforts can lead to more efficient and cost-effective energy use. Various actions that can promote the sustainable development of an industrial energy community were discussed, considering both economic and energy perspectives. Topics included innovative financing mechanisms, regulatory frameworks, technological solutions, and best practices from successful case studies. The overall objective was to provide a comprehensive understanding of how industries can collaborate with communities to create resilient, sustainable energy systems that benefit all stakeholders.

For more information, you can find the event's agenda and the PowerPoint presentation used to introduce ePLANET in the annexes (3.3.1 Activity 1).

More than 200 participants were registered, with 150 of them attending simultaneously. Participants represented SMEs located in industrial sites, the Catalan public administration, and other stakeholders. You can access the recording [here](#).

Figure 2-6 - Girona 1st activity event banner

Figure 2-7 - Girona 1st activity webinar screenshot

2.3.2 Activity 2: Innovative financing - Focus on Interprovincial transport and mobility

The regional council of Girona (DDGI) organised its second scale-up activity in collaboration with Prospect + in a webinar format and was held in Catalan on the 28th of May 2024. Olga Barranchina, an expert from LIMA, moderated the event and gave a general introduction to the ePLANET project.

The agenda of the meeting was focused on innovative financing for interprovincial transport and mobility actions from Sustainable Climate and Energy Action Plans (SECAPs). During this webinar, several strategies implemented by various municipalities in Catalonia and across Spain were presented, along with alternative financing methods they applied. Participants were able to identify opportunities for innovative European financing in the mobility sector but also evaluate proposals for improving state public incentives for electric mobility, and assess the effectiveness of incentives for shared electric mobility.

For more information, you can find the agenda of the event and the PowerPoint presentation used to introduce ePLANET in the annexes (3.3.2 Activity 2).

This activity gathered 40 participants, including representatives from the Catalan Public Administration and stakeholders providing mobility services. You can access the recording [here](#).

28 de Maig del 2024, 11h00

Webinar
Estratègies i finançament innovador en mobilitat local i interprovincial dels PAESCs

Diputació de Girona

ePLANET

Amb la participació de:

AEDIVE, guppy, Diputació de Girona, Ajuntament de Valladolid, PROSPECT+

Cal inscripció prèvia

Figure 2-8 - Banner Girona 2nd activity

Contratos de rendimiento energético (EPC)

- Esquema de financiación innovador para la implementación de **proyectos de energía sostenible**, en el que una **Empresa de Servicios Energéticos (ESCO)** ejecuta todos los pasos del proyecto y ofrece una garantía de desempeño en ahorros de energía (kWh).
- La ESCO financia las mejoras de eficiencia energética en función del ahorro energético garantizado que se generará en el futuro (€). En principio, la ESCO solo recibirá una tarifa de servicio (€) y obtendrá su retorno de inversión una vez que el proyecto genere ahorros de energía.

Ventajas

1. Los riesgos de inversión se transfieren a la ESCO.
2. Rendimiento energético garantizado.
3. Requiere una baja (o ninguna) inversión/capital inicial del cliente.
4. Servicio llave en mano para el cliente.
5. Puede incluir también otras soluciones no energéticas

Figure 2-9 - Screenshot Girona 2nd activity

2.3.3 Key takeaways and learnings from Girona scale-up activities

- The high participation and acceptance in the activity of creating energy communities in industrial environments confirmed the growing interest in this topic among companies and local authorities. In this sense, from the Provincial Council of Girona and the energy transition offices, we can inform and provide support or even connect companies from the same industrial estate that are interested in creating this type of energy community.
- The mobility financing webinar helped local authorities and neighbourhood communities learn about innovative car sharing formulas such as Som Mobiliat to be able to implement efficient measures in environments or areas with few public transport connections.

2.4 Crete activities

2.4.1 Activity 1: Innovative financing - Focus on Energy Efficiency and Buildings

The Centre for Renewable Energy Sources and Saving Foundation (CRES) organised Crete's first scale-up activity in collaboration with Prospect + in a webinar format on the 7th of February 2024. It was held in Greek. Katerina Sfakianaki moderated the session and gave an introduction on ePLANET project.

This webinar addressed one of the capacity-building needs identified in Task 4.1, which is financing mechanisms for energy efficiency projects. The target audience was represented by representatives of regions, municipalities, and other public bodies involved in the planning, implementation, and financing of energy transition plans and energy-saving projects for public buildings.

The participants gained a better understanding of various financing mechanisms for energy efficiency projects, such as Energy Performance Contracts and EU best practices demonstrated by projects like REFINE. They also explored case studies from the EU-funded projects PRODESA and SMAFIN/SMAFIN. Overall, it was an opportunity to grasp the outcomes and prospects of energy-saving initiatives in buildings, particularly those focusing on municipal structures. Additionally, the course aimed to equip learners with insights into capacity-building programs like PROSPECT+ designed to empower public authorities in financing sustainable energy plans. Through these topics, participants developed the knowledge to navigate and contribute to the field of energy efficiency financing more effectively. They were also able to learn more about one of ePLANET best practice: Prospect + capacity building.

For more information, you can find the agenda of the event and the power point presentation used to introduce ePLANET results in the annexes (3.4.1 Activity 1).

This activity gathered 38 participants, mainly from municipalities, regional authorities, universities, companies and EU organisations. You can access the recording [here](#).

The banner features a photograph of a modern multi-story apartment building with balconies and a well-maintained garden with pink flowers. At the top, logos for KAPE CRES (ΚΕΝΤΡΟ ΑΝΑΘΕΣΙΜΩΝ ΠΗΓΩΝ ΚΑΙ ΕΣΟΚΟΝΟΜΗΣΗΣ ΕΝΕΡΓΕΙΑΣ), ePLANET, and PROSPECT+ are displayed. The main text reads: 'WEBINAR: INNOVATIVE FINANCING FOR BUILDINGS' ENERGY EFFICIENCY PROJECTS'. Below this, the date 'WEDNESDAY 07 FEBRUARY 2024' and time '13:00 - 15:00 Greek time' are listed. A 'REGISTRATION' button with a QR code is provided. At the bottom right, the European Union logo and the text 'Funded by the European Union' are visible.

Figure 2-10 - Banner Crete 1st activity

Figure 2-11 - Screenshot Crete 1st activity

2.4.2 Activity 2: Methodologies and tools for planning and prioritising energy savings interventions at local level

The Centre for Renewable Energy Sources and Saving Foundation (CRES) organised Crete second scale-up activity as an in-person and open workshop on the 19th of April 2024 in Athens and in collaboration with re-MODULES project and SYMPRAXIS team. It was held in Greek. Katerina Sfakianaki from CRES was the one representing ePLANET, she gave a presentation on the projects results and achievements on the platform.

During the event, the main tools that were developed in the framework of re-MODULEES and ePLANET H2020 projects were presented as well as good practices of energy transition projects at European and national level. The re-MODULEES project's main objective is the formulation of a market activation scheme for energy renovation of residential buildings at national and European levels. Building on the key results of previous European projects, an online platform has been developed, which will help make building renovations easier, faster, and more attractive for those concerned.

The ePLANET project aims to improve coordination between municipalities and regions in order to optimise the decision-making process. The digitalisation of the energy consumption data of the existing building stock and the development of a comprehensive energy management system was carried out in the Municipalities of Crete and the data of SECAPs were captured in a specially designed platform, facilitating the planning of future actions to accelerate the energy transition.

For more information, you can find the event's agenda and the PowerPoint presentation used to introduce ePLANET results in the annexes (3.4.2 Activity 2).

This activity gathered 21 participants, comprising local national stakeholders, industry experts, and citizens. It brought together a wide range of stakeholders, including government officials, industry experts, and concerned citizens. Since it was an in-person event, we don't have

recordings of the sessions but we have pictures and a video testimonial from Katerina Sfakianaki available [here](#).

Figure 2-12 - Crete 2nd activity

Figure 2-13 - Crete 2nd activity ePLANET presentation

2.4.3 Key takeaways and learnings from Crete scale-up activities

- From the first activity:
 - Governance structures are very important for the achievement of energy transition goals as the sharing of harmonised information between authorities is important for the planning and implementation of energy transition measures.
 - In an energy-saving performance contract, the energy service provider guarantees the project's energy savings and financial benefit. Therefore, the provider's remuneration is based on the achievement of the guaranteed energy savings.
 - In Greece, there are funding mechanisms and useful tools for citizens to renovate their residences, but they face complex and slow administrative processes.
- From the second activity:
 - Governance structures are very important for the achievement of energy transition goals as the sharing of harmonised information between authorities is important for the planning and implementation of energy transition measures.
 - Innovative online platforms developed in the framework of European projects are useful tools for one-stop decision-making for the energy renovation of

buildings, as the user can identify the best interventions in terms of energy benefits and costs.

- The construction sector can effectively contribute to the energy transition of local communities, not only by providing its products and services but also by certifying the quality and energy efficiency of energy interventions in buildings.

3 Annexes

3.1 Template report

ePLANET capacity-building and scale-up activities
Event report

To be returned at the latest 7 working days after the event to:
nadege.seguel@fedarene.org
& esti@threeoclock.co

Event type (workshop/webinar):	
Event title:	
Event date:	
ePLANET partner in charge:	
Name of the speaker:	
Location:	
Language:	
Number and type of participants:	
Short description of the event:	
ePLANET content presented:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Showcase of ePLANET platform ○ Presentation of governance concepts ○ Invitation to next Stakeholder Forums ○ Best practices ○ Local energy community ○ Promotion of MoU ○ Other:
Link to the presentation, agenda, pictures, and participants list:	
Link to the recording (short explanation if not possible):	
Key takeaways or learnings:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. 2. 3.
Additional remarks:	

Please upload all relevant materials in the corresponding folder in Nextcloud:
<https://nextcloud.tech.beegroup-cimne.com/s/mRyMq6g9a7pRePz>

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Figure 3-1 - Template report

3.2 Zlín region activities

3.2.1 Activity 1

CEJIZA, s.r.o. si Vás dovoluje pozvat na mezikrajské pracovní setkání osob zabývajících se energetikou pro jednotlivé kraje v ČR konané pod záštitou hejtmána Jihomoravského kraje Mgr. Jana Grolicha

„ENERGIE U KULATÉHO STOLU“

ve čtvrtek 9. 11. 2023 od 9:30 do 16:00 hodin
v areálu Moravian Science Centre Brno, příspěvková organizace, Křížkovského 554/12, Brno

PROGRAM
PŘÍJEZD ÚČASTNÍKŮ (9.00 – 9.30 hodin)

DOPOLEDNÍ BLOK

1. Úvodní slovo
2. Pohled na aktuální energetickou situaci v ČR a v EU (Ing. Jiří Gavor, CSC., jednatel ENA s.r.o. a výkonný ředitel Asociace nezávislých dodavatelů energií)
3. Kombinovaný nákup energií na burze PXE (Ing. František Dědič, vedoucí odboru hospodářské a majetkové správy; Jihočeský kraj)
4. Nákup elektrické energie – problém nebo příležitost? (Tomáš Jílek, předseda představenstva Technologie hlavního města Prahy, a.s.)

ODPOLEDNÍ BLOK

1. Digitalizace procesu sběru a správy dat (Ing. Bořek Dvořáček, referent pro energetiku, Královéhradecký kraj)
2. Nová státní energetická koncepce (Ing. Tomáš Voříšek, technický ředitel, SEVEN Energy, s.r.o.)
3. Mezikrajská koordinace, založení platformy energetického managementu (Mgr. David Matuška, energetický manažer, vedoucí oddělení, Energetické centrum Ústeckého kraje, příspěvková organizace)
4. Ukončení, slovo na závěr

CÍLE SETKÁNÍ

- výměna zkušeností v oblasti energetiky
- setkání a posílení vzájemných vztahů

Účast, prosím, potvrďte do 27. 10. 2023 na info@cejiza.cz.
Účast na setkání je bezplatná. Z důvodu zachování pracovního charakteru akce je však účast omezena na **nejvýše 2 osoby** z každého kraje.
Občerstvení v průběhu setkání je zajištěno.

CEJIZA, s.r.o.
Žerotínovo náměstí 449/3, 602 00 Brno, kontaktní adresa Jaselská 205/25, 602 00 Brno,
IČO 28353242; tel.: +420 530 506 206

CEJIZA, s.r.o. je společností založenou jediným zakladatelem – Jihomoravským krajem. Tomuto kraji a krajským příspěvkovým organizacím poskytuje servis již od roku 2009. Významná část činnosti společnosti se týká oblasti energetiky – provádí výběr dodavatelů elektřiny a zemního plynu a též administrativně spravuje odběrná místa těchto dvou komodit. Více informací o společnosti na www.cejiza.cz.

Figure 3-2 - Agenda 1st interregional energy platform

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Figure 3-3 - Slides 1-6

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Figure 3-4 - Slides 7-12

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Figure 3-5 - Slides 13-18

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CÍL - ČISTOTA OVZDUŠÍ

- Úspory energie
- Modernizace budov, zdrojů tepla a TV
- Instalace OZE
- Výstavba budov v pasivním a plusovém standardu
- Územní plánování
- Udržitelná doprava
- Podpora lokální energetiky a ekonomiky
- Dotační politika a legislativa

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Figure 3-6 -Slides 19-22

3.2.2 Activity 2

ENERGETICKÁ PLATFORMA KRAJŮ ČR

si Vás dovoluje pozvat na

1. setkání platformy (leden 2024)

11.1.2024

9:00 - 13:00

**ZM P1.412 FRANTIŠKA KUPKY, BUDOVA KŮ
REGIOCENTRUM NOVÝ PIVOVAR
PIVOVARSKÉ NÁM. 1245, HRADEC KRÁLOVÉ**

Program setkání

- 08:30 - 09:00** prezence účastníků
- 09:00 - 09:10**
 - zahájení - zástupce hostitele (Centrum investic, rozvoje a inovací/Královehradecký kraj)
- 09:10 - 9:30**
 - úvodní seznámení, představení účastníků
- 09:30 - 10:30**
 - definování oblastí spolupráce, moderovaná diskuze (Mgr. David Matuška, ECUK)
- 10:30 - 11:00**
 - přestávka, občerstvení, networking
- 11:00 - 12:30**
 - výměna zkušeností (výstavba inteligentních budov, instalace OZE (koncepce/strategie jednotlivých krajů), instalace nabíjecích stanic, účast na přípravě investic kraje, aplikace na energetický management), moderovaná diskuze (Mgr. David Matuška, ECUK)
- 12:30 - 13:00** závěr, rozloučení

Váš zájem o účast (max. 2 účastníci za organizaci) prosím sdělte do 4. 1. 2024 zde:
<https://forms.gle/AFfNiORSwzoHgfix8>

Energetické centrum
Ústeckého kraje

energie pod kontrolou

ENERGETICKÁ AGENTURA
ZLÍNSKÉHO KRAJE, s.p.s.

CENTRUM
INVESTIC, ROZVOJE
A INOVACÍ
OD MYŠLENKY K REALIZACI

Figure 3-7 - Agenda 2nd energy platform

Zlínský kraj
 Rozvoj projektů ve Zlínském kraji a Jejich financování
 Energetická platforma krajů ČR
 01. 01. 2024 Hradec Králové

ePLANET
 Horizon 2020
 European Union Funding
 for Research & Innovation

Energetické úspory
 Základní škola
 Nový Hrozenkov

Plánovaná úspora energie: 394,20 GJ/rok
 Snížení spotřeby energie na vytápění o 63,95 %

ePLANET

Rekonstrukce
 kulturního domu
 ve Stráži

Zateplení obvodových stěn, střešní a podlahy na terasu, výměna výplně, výměna stroje tepla a úprava otopné soustavy, instalace VZT a rekuperaci, rekonstrukce zádveří, instalace fotovoltaických panelů, osazení střešní techniky, zateplení střechy.

ePLANET

14 | 15 Batův Institut –
 instalace
 fotovoltaických systémů

Předpokládaná úspora energie: 627,08 GJ/rok
 Nový instalovaný epitchový výkon: 103,80 kWp

ePLANET

Stanice Holešov –
 výstavba nové stanice

První veřejná budova v pasivním standardu ve Zlínském kraji
 o celkové podlahové ploše 1 138 m²
 Celková výše dotace z Evropského fondu pro regionální rozvoj: 14 964 160 Kč
 potřeba tepla na vytápění <15kWh/m²

ePLANET

Stanice Bystřice pod
 Hostýnem
 - výstavba nové stanice

Polární stanice P2 v pasivním standardu
 o celkové podlahové ploše 1 078,8 m²
 Celková výše dotace z Evropského fondu pro regionální rozvoj: 13 361 837 Kč
 potřeba tepla na vytápění <15kWh/m²

ePLANET

Multifunkční areál
 Zubří - Lékařský dům

Lékařský dům v pasivním standardu
 o celkové podlahové ploše 1 091,30 m², potřeba tepla na vytápění <15kWh/m²

ePLANET

Multifunkční areál
 Zubří - Lékařský dům

Lékařský dům v pasivním standardu
 Celková výše dotace z Fondu soudržnosti: 14 942 108,07 Kč

ePLANET

Multifunkční areál
 Zubří - DPS

Dům pro seniory v pasivním standardu
 o celkové podlahové ploše 1 213,40 m², potřeba tepla na vytápění <15kWh/m²

ePLANET

Multifunkční areál
 Zubří - DPS

Dům pro seniory v pasivním standardu
 Celková výše dotace z Fondu soudržnosti: 15 150 757,06 Kč

ePLANET

Figure 3-8 - Slides 1-10

Zateplení a rekonstrukce budovy č.26 KHS Zlín / Ředitelství KNTB a.s.

Část KNTB
Předpokládaná úspora energie: 627,00 GJ/rok
Snížení spotřeby energie na vytápění o 44,70 %

Zateplení a rekonstrukce budovy č.26 KHS Zlín / Ředitelství KNTB a.s.

Část KHS
Předpokládaná úspora energie: 730,00 GJ/rok
Snížení spotřeby energie na vytápění o 42,02 %

Zateplení a rekonstrukce budovy č.26 KHS Zlín / Ředitelství KNTB a.s.

Část KHS: FVE + VZT
Předpokládaná úspora energie: 75,00 GJ/rok
Nový instalovaný apítkový výkon FVE: 19,25 kWp
Snížení spotřeby energie na vytápění o 5,06 %

Výstavba tělocvičny pro ZŠ Nový Hrozenkov

Obestavěný prostor: 6 940 m³
Kapacita: 245 osob

Výstavba tělocvičny pro ZŠ Nový Hrozenkov

Výzva Ministerstva financí
Podpora rozvoje a obnovy materiálně-technické základny regionálního školství v působnosti obcí
Celková investice: 40 000 000 Kč
Celková dotace: 20 000 000 Kč

Výstavba tělocvičny pro ZŠ Nový Hrozenkov

Výzva Ministerstva financí
Podpora rozvoje a obnovy materiálně-technické základny regionálního školství v působnosti obcí

Mateřská škola v areálu Krajské nemocnice T. Bati, a.s.

Kapacita podporovaných zařízení: páče o děti nebo vzdělávacích zařízení: 50 osob

Operační program Evropská unie
Operační program pro MŠMT
Regionální operační program ČR

Mateřská škola v areálu Krajské nemocnice T. Bati, a.s.

Celková investice: 33 000 000 Kč
Dotace IROP: 31 868 820,00 Kč

Operační program Evropská unie
Operační program pro MŠMT
Regionální operační program ČR

OPŽP 61.výzva Přístavba knihovny v Rožnově

Pasivní standard přístavby budovy knihovny

Zlínský kraj

Přístavba městské knihovny v pasivním standardu

stav po realizaci
- investice 44 mil. Kč, z toho dotace na pasivní standard 50% - 22 mil. Kč
- Slavnostní otevření 15.03.2023

Figure 3-9 - Slides 11-20

Výzva ENERGov č. 2/2023 – Energetické úspory památkově chráněných budov

Přijem žádostí: 16.10.2023 – 29.2.2024 **Alokace:** 2 000 000 000 Kč

Výzva se vztahuje poskytnutí a fyzických osob a podniků výzvy žadatel:

Indikátor	A ₁	A ₂
Úspora primární energie (včetně tepelné energie)	1,5%	1,5%
Každá kmenová jednotka energie	> 10%	> 10%

Podmínky poskytnutí: 1.301 Kč, 2.301 Kč, 3.301 Kč, 4.301 Kč, 5.301 Kč, 6.301 Kč, 7.301 Kč, 8.301 Kč, 9.301 Kč, 10.301 Kč, 11.301 Kč, 12.301 Kč, 13.301 Kč, 14.301 Kč, 15.301 Kč, 16.301 Kč, 17.301 Kč, 18.301 Kč, 19.301 Kč, 20.301 Kč, 21.301 Kč, 22.301 Kč, 23.301 Kč, 24.301 Kč, 25.301 Kč, 26.301 Kč, 27.301 Kč, 28.301 Kč, 29.301 Kč, 30.301 Kč, 31.301 Kč, 32.301 Kč, 33.301 Kč, 34.301 Kč, 35.301 Kč, 36.301 Kč, 37.301 Kč, 38.301 Kč, 39.301 Kč, 40.301 Kč, 41.301 Kč, 42.301 Kč, 43.301 Kč, 44.301 Kč, 45.301 Kč, 46.301 Kč, 47.301 Kč, 48.301 Kč, 49.301 Kč, 50.301 Kč, 51.301 Kč, 52.301 Kč, 53.301 Kč, 54.301 Kč, 55.301 Kč, 56.301 Kč, 57.301 Kč, 58.301 Kč, 59.301 Kč, 60.301 Kč, 61.301 Kč, 62.301 Kč, 63.301 Kč, 64.301 Kč, 65.301 Kč, 66.301 Kč, 67.301 Kč, 68.301 Kč, 69.301 Kč, 70.301 Kč, 71.301 Kč, 72.301 Kč, 73.301 Kč, 74.301 Kč, 75.301 Kč, 76.301 Kč, 77.301 Kč, 78.301 Kč, 79.301 Kč, 80.301 Kč, 81.301 Kč, 82.301 Kč, 83.301 Kč, 84.301 Kč, 85.301 Kč, 86.301 Kč, 87.301 Kč, 88.301 Kč, 89.301 Kč, 90.301 Kč, 91.301 Kč, 92.301 Kč, 93.301 Kč, 94.301 Kč, 95.301 Kč, 96.301 Kč, 97.301 Kč, 98.301 Kč, 99.301 Kč, 100.301 Kč

Fotovoltaika na budově ČOV v obci Horní Němč

Objem energie: 30,17 GWh
Nový instalovaný fotovoltaický výkon: 1,1 kWp
Roční úspora energie: 11,62 %

Kotelna na biomasu BTH Sleviňov

Zdroj tepla pro šávkův – energetický mix – dřevní štěpka KAHČ, vstřik h voze + nové je instalována PVIE o výkonu 130 kWp a baterie o kapacitě 130 kWh

Kotelna na biomasu v obci Rožín

Kotelna o celkovém výkonu 4 000 kW (základní 1 600 kW) spaluje obilnou slámu Účinnost výroby tepla: 88 % Výroba tepla: 14 855 GWh/rok

Téměř energeticky soběstačná obec Hostětín

Kotelna na dřevní štěpku o celkovém výkonu 786 kW spaluje odřevňovací odpady – dřevní štěpku. Fotovoltaické systémy na střechách i v obcích kateřiny. Energetické všechny obecní budovy, pasivní standard Energetického centra VERONICA, kotlovna ČOV

TOT Otrokovice energetické využití odpadu

Projektová cena zpracování 6 000 tun odpadů za rok (žay z ČOV a podzemní jednotkové plasty), zatím výstavby projekt

TOT Otrokovice energetické využití odpadu

Kotel s dvojnásobným hořákem spojuje výrobní plyn nebo olej a dodává 22 GWh/rok do síť Tepelný Otrokovice, odpadním produktem je i vodík

Nákup elektromobilů

PENB – Racková 37. výzva OPŽP

Stávající budova prodává se 30 let. Stávající bude kompletně rekonstruována. Bude zachována prodejna a podkrovní. Bude rozšířena o šestý křídlo zastřešený obvodové okny STKS EPS 705 ledy 200 mm (STKS PIR/PUR 140 mm), křídlo budovy zastřešené dřev. a pánevkou 4,5x60 mm s EPS 3005 30 mm. Střecha budovy zastřešená 100 mm EPS 1005 + EPS s ledy 200 mm s ugražací střechou. Výhled střešní na 10 a 2 budovy šikmými světlými fasádami. Bude realizována nová odpadní soustava – podlahová/otopná ústředí, také 50/60°C, zdroj tepla led čerpadlo vakuové-voda MW, akumulace 100 l. Přívod teple vody – nepřímotopný ohřev 200 l vlnitý + čerpadlo s rekuperací prodává, šatny a podkrovní. WC – podlahové vlnitý, ořad – dřevěný vlnitý. Čištění prodává a podkrovní – multiplet. Ověřené LED. Na střeše instalována fotovoltaika 17,5 kWp.

Výzva ENERGov č. 3/2023 – Efektivní výstavba škol

Nová budova v pasivním energetickém standardu tj. se i přístavě a náhraně bude dosahovat následující hodnoty energetických ukazatelů

Stavbaž ukazatel	Podle normy budova
Přívod tepla střešní při šikmém svahu 50 Pa	max 0,4 W/m ²
Podlahový součinitel prostupu tepla	0,10 W/m ² K
Měrná potřeba tepla na vytápění ¹⁾ – průměrná výška budovy ²⁾ 4 m	2,15 kWh/m ² ·a
Měrná potřeba tepla na vytápění ¹⁾ – průměrná výška budovy ²⁾ 8 m	2,20 kWh/m ² ·a
Měrná potřeba tepla na chlazení ¹⁾	2,15 kWh/m ² ·a
Teplota čerpané teple vody v zimě ¹⁾ v zimě ¹⁾ v letním období	65/30°C
Podkrovní energie v rekonstruované střeše	Kapitola 6.1.1.1

1) Výpočet vypočítá měrnou potřebu tepla na vytápění při standardní teplotě vzduchu v místnosti a teplotě teple vody na vytápění a teplotu čerpané teple vody při 4 m až 8 m výškové třídě (teplota čerpané teple vody 10 m, 13 m, 16 m, 19 m, 22 m, 25 m, 28 m, 31 m, 34 m, 37 m, 40 m, 43 m, 46 m, 49 m, 52 m, 55 m, 58 m, 61 m, 64 m, 67 m, 70 m, 73 m, 76 m, 79 m, 82 m, 85 m, 88 m, 91 m, 94 m, 97 m, 100 m)

2) Průměrná výška budovy se stanovuje jako střední hodnota výšky všech křídlových a energeticky uzávěrných částí.

Figure 3-10 - Slides 21-30

3.3 Girona activities

3.3.1 Activity 1

Webinar - Comunitats energètiques en polígons industrials		2 / 2
AGENDA:		
Dia: 27 de Febrer del 2024, de 12h a 13h30		
Moderadora: Olga Barrachina i Salleras (Associació LIMA)		
Presentació	Ponent	Durada
Benvinguda i introducció	Olga Barrachina (Associació LIMA)	5 min
<u>Bloc 1 - Potencials d'autoconsum compartit d'energies renovables</u>		
Comunitats energètiques en polígons industrials	Jaume Castellà (EPI)	10 min
Xarxes de calor en polígons industrials a l'àrea de Barcelona	Alex Ivancic (AIGUASOL)	10 min
Anàlisi de la capacitat fotovoltaica als polígons industrials del Bages	Josep Rosell (OICOS)	10 min
SIE-Comunitat: digitalització de la promoció, disseny i gestió de comunitats energètiques	Sergi Pérez (INERGY)	10 min
<u>Bloc 2 - Casos reals del nostre territori i eines</u>		
Comunitat energètica al polígon industrial de Rosanes	Marcela Véliz (AEPIR)	10 min
Comunitats energètiques - model de negoci bio-circular	Sami Rtimi Sboui (Alcarràs Bioproductors)	10 min
Empreses del PAES claus per la transformació i el futur econòmic del territori i la transició energètica	Montserrat Ambrós Fuentes (Associació d'empresaris de Bufalvent)	10 min
<u>Torn de preguntes</u>		15 min
Tancament		

ePLANET GA n° 101032450

Figure 3-12 - Agenda Girona 1st activity

Webinar
Les comunitats energètiques en polígons industrials

27 de Febrer 2024, 12h00 CET

Programa

Presentació	Parlant	Durada
Introducció i presentació	Olga Benavente (Associació LIMA)	8 min
Comunitats energètiques en polígons industrials	Josana Corralis (AER)	10 min
Zones de refer en polígons industrials a l'Índex de Sostenibilitat	Alba Ferrer (INDUSTRIAL)	10 min
Anàlisi de la capacitat tecnològica en polígons industrials del Segre	Sergi Ferrer (EPCOE)	10 min
El Sector digitalitzat de la promoció, ús i gestió de comunitats energètiques	Sergi Ferrer (EPCOE)	10 min
Èxit 2 – Cases reals del sector terciari i sector		
Comunitat energètica al polígon industrial de Suroest	Amanda Valls (AER)	10 min
Comunitat energètica i model de negoci del sector	Sergi Ferrer (EPCOE)	10 min
Projecció del TMB clau per la transició (alhora acció del territori i la transició energètica)	(Marta Espinosa), (Marta Espinosa)	10 min
Totals i conclusions	(Associació d'Empreses de Solució)	10 min

XARXA D'AUTORITATS PÚBLIQUES LOCALS PER A L'IMPULS DE LA TRANSICIÓ ENERGÈTICA

Dades clau

- Projecte europeu, convocatòria Horizon 2020
- Calendaris 05/2021 – 06/2024

Consort

- CIMNE (CAT, coordinador)
- ICADN (CAT)
- Diputació de Girona (CAT, pilot)
- Associació LIMA (CAT)
- FEARNE (Belgès)
- ICLIS (Alemany)
- THREZOOLOGY (França)
- Agència d'energia de la regió de Zúric (República Txeca, pilot)
- Fons de desenvolupament regional de Crèta (Grècia, pilot)
- + 6 follow-up regions (incl. Consell Comarcal Baix Llobregat)

Objectiu

- Establiment d'una plataforma d'intercanvi d'informació relativa als plans i accions de transició energètica, transparent i coherent, per a la integració de dades i la comparació de diferents mesures.
- Promoció d'un model de governança de grup "clusters geogràfics", que afavoreixi la creació de grups de treball multinivell d'entitats públiques (local, regional) i entitats col·laboradores per al desenvolupament i actualització dels plans de transició energètica.
- Digitalització dels plans i accions de transició energètica de les administracions públiques, incloent l'harmonització de les accions (taxonomia).
- Creació, suport i institucionalització dels grups de treball multinivell per tal d'afavorir l'adopció i desplegament de mesures de transició energètica de forma coordinada.

Resultats

- Estratègia de "clustering governance" per a la Transició Energètica (→ PATR a Catalunya)
- Plataforma per a la gestió i monitoratge de PAESC (fase final, desplegament)
- Repositori de bones pràctiques i solucions per a la Transició Energètica (en desenvolupament)
- Webinars i workshops de capacitat i sensibilització (en curs, Girona → Catalunya)
- Disseminació via articles, publicacions, participació a conferències

Finalitzat en el darrer semestre de projecte

Capacity Building Programme
Girona Province
2023-2024

Flowchart showing the structure of the Capacity Building Programme with 10 numbered steps.

Figure 3-13 - Slides 1-8 Girona 1st activity

Xarxes socials

- [@ePlanetH2020](#)
- [ePLANET_Linkedin](#)
- [ePLANET_project_YouTube](#)
- www.eplanetH2020.eu

Programa

Presentador	Paraula	Durada
Benvinguda i introducció	Olga Benavent (Universitat LMU)	7 min
Blau 1 - Potencial d'autoconsum compartit d'energies renovables		
Comunitats energètiques en polígons industrials	Josua Corral (IFE)	10 min
Exemples de neteja en polígons industrials a l'illa de Eivissa	Àlex Ferrer (SOLARIS)	10 min
Anàlisi de la viabilitat tècnica i econòmica dels polígons industrials del Segura	Jaume Sureda (DINOR)	10 min
El Concepte d'Integració de la producció, el consum i el magatzem d'energies renovables	Jaume Sureda (DINOR)	10 min
Blau 2 - Casos reals del sector tèxtil i altres		
Comunitat energètica al polígon industrial de Suroeste	Marta Valls (IFE)	10 min
Comunitat energètica: model de negoci més sostenible	Enric Sureda (SOLARIS)	10 min
Exposició del TSEI clau per la transició i el futur sostenible del sector i la transició energètica	Montserrat Andreu Ferrer (Associació d'empreses de Sabadell)	10 min
Tancament		10 min

Figure 3-14 - Slides 9-11 Girona 1st activity

3.3.2 Activity 2

Webinar -Estratègies i finançament innovador en mobilitat local i interprovincial dels PAESCS		2 / 2
AGENDA:		
Dia: 28 de Maig del 2024, de 11h a 12h30		
Organitzat per: Diputació de Girona, Associació LIMA, Three o'clock		
Moderadora: Olga Barrachina i Salleras (ESTRATS)		
Presentació	Ponent	
Benvinguda i introducció	ESTRATS	
Bloc 1 - Avançant en la Mobilitat Sostenible: Estratègies i Finançament Innovador		
Oportunitades de financiación innovadora y europea en el sector de la movilidad	PROSPECT +	
Propuesta de mejora de incentivos públicos estatales en la movilidad eléctrica	AEDIVE	
Bloc 2 - Casos d'exemple i eines		
Mobilitat compartida a la Comunitat Energètica de Balenyà	SOM MOBILITAT	
Incentius per a la mobilitat elèctrica del Pra	SOM MOBILITAT	
Incentivos para la Movilidad Eléctrica en Valladolid	Ayuntamiento de Valladolid	
Aplicación de movilidad compartida en colaboración público privada en Gijon	Guppy	
Torn de preguntes		
Tancament		

Figure 3-15 - Agenda Girona 2nd activity

ESTRATÈGIES I FINANÇAMENT INNOVADOR EN MOBILITAT LOCAL I INTERPROVINCIAL DELS PAESCS

Project co-funded by the European Union Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme GA 101032450. The sole responsibility of this video lies with the authors (ePLANET consortium). The European Union is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

ePLANET

28 de Maig del 2024, 11h00

Webinar
Estratègies en finançament innovador en mobilitat local i interprovincial

Diputació de Girona

amb la participació de:

Three smaller ePLANET project posters showing various activities and partners.

ePLANET

The Objective: To develop a set of strategies and actions that will help municipalities to...
The Strategy: To develop a set of strategies and actions that will help municipalities to...
The Training activities: 7 main activities...
603 municipalities participating in the project
764 projects developed
129 municipalities participating in the project
7 projects developed

ePLANET

XARXA D'AUTORITATS PÚBLIQUES LOCALS PER A L'IMPULS DE LA TRANSICIÓ ENERGÈTICA

Resultats:

- Estratègia de "clustering governance" per a la Transició Energètica (→ PAESC a Catalunya)
- Plataforma per a la gestió i monitoratge de PAESC (fase final, desplegament)
- Repositori de bones pràctiques i solucions per a la Transició Energètica (en desenvolupament)
- Webinars i workshops de capacitat i sensibilització (en curs, Girona → Catalunya)
- Disseminació via articles, publicacions, participació a conferències

Difusió en el darrer semestre de projecte

ePLANET

4 de Junio, de 10:00 a 13:00 CEST

Webinar
Qué viene después de un PACES? Implementación y monitoreo

Governament de Catalunya

en col·laboració amb:

Covenant of Mayors for Climate & Energy EUROPE

Eventos con inscripción previa

10th June 2024 at 13:00 - Brussels

ePLANET Open Event:
How to accelerate the deployment of Energy Transition to fulfil the 2030 and 2050 Energy Goals

with the participation of:

- Covenant of Mayors - Europe
- RESCHOOL project
- IN-PLAN project
- REGIO 1st project

Registration required

organized by: Governament de Catalunya, Institut Català d'Energia, CARTENE, LIMA

Xarxes socials

Twitter: @Planet2020
LinkedIn: ePLANET LinkedIn
YouTube: ePLANET_project Youtube
Website: www.eplanet2020.eu

Programa

Activitat i Objectiu	Responsables
Revisió de l'estat de l'evolució de les polítiques energètiques i de les mesures de transició energètica i accions en el sector de la mobilitat	PAESC +
Proposició de mesures de transició pública orientades a la mobilitat sostenible	PAESC
Revisió de les polítiques energètiques i de les mesures de transició energètica i accions en el sector de la mobilitat	PAESC +
Revisió de les polítiques energètiques i de les mesures de transició energètica i accions en el sector de la mobilitat	PAESC +
Revisió de les polítiques energètiques i de les mesures de transició energètica i accions en el sector de la mobilitat	PAESC +
Revisió de les polítiques energètiques i de les mesures de transició energètica i accions en el sector de la mobilitat	PAESC +

ePLANET

www.eplanet2020.eu

Figure 3-16 - Girona 2nd activity slides 1-10

3.4 Crete activities

3.4.1 Activity 1

KAPE CRES | CENTRE FOR RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCES AND SAVING

WEBINAR

Innovative financing for Buildings' Energy Efficiency projects
*In the context of EU project e-PLANET
 (European Public Local Authorities' Network for Driving the Energy Transition)*

Wednesday 07 February 2024
 13:00-15:00 Greek time (12:00-14:00 CET)

Agenda

13:00-13:20	Introduction to ePLANET <i>Katerina Sfakianaki, Building Physicist MSc, Division of Development Programs, CRES</i>
13:20-13:40	Financing energy efficiency projects through Energy Performance Contracts, EU best practices – the REFINE project <i>Aristotelis Botzios-Valaskakis, Mechanical Engineer MSc, Division of Development Programs, CRES</i>
13:40-14:00	Financing energy saving projects in Greek buildings. One Stop Shop - The SMAFIN project <i>Kiki Papadopoulou, Head of Dissemination of RES & EE Applications Department, SMAFIN Project Manager, CRES</i>
14:00-14:20	Energy renovation of Municipal buildings in Vari, Voula, Vouliagmeni through Energy Performance Contracting – The PRODESA project <i>Argyro Giakoumi, Physicist MSc, Energy Policy Analysis Department, CRES</i>
14:20-14:40	Innovative financial approaches for cities and regions – The PROSPECT+ project <i>University of Pireaus Research Centre (to be confirmed)</i>
14:40-15:00	Discussion – Close

PARTNERSHIP COORDINATOR

PARTNERS

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101032450.

Figure 3-17 - Crete Island agenda activity 1

ePLANET
EUROPEAN PUBLIC LOCAL AUTHORITIES' NETWORK FOR DRIVING THE ENERGY TRANSITION
Το Ευρωπαϊκό έργο ePLANET
ΚΑΤΕ CRES CENTRE FOR RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCES AND SKILLS
Κατερίνα Στρακωνάκη, Φυσικός Κατασκευαστικό Περιβάλλοντος, ΚΕΚ
Διαδραστικό Σχημάτιο 07.02.2024

Το έργο ePLANET

European Public Local Authorities' Network for driving the Energy Transition
Πρόγραμμα: Horizon 2020, CSA - Coordination and support action
Θεματικός: LC-SC3-EC-5-2020 - Supporting public authorities in driving the energy transition
Διάρκεια: 3 έτη (1 Σεπτεμβρίου 2021 - 31 Αυγούστου 2024)
Συνολικός π/υ: - € 1,5 εκ.

Διαδραστικό Σχημάτιο 07.02.2024

10 εταίροι - 6 Ευρωπαϊκές χώρες

- CIMNE (International Centre for Numerical methods in Engineering), Ισπανία
- ICAE (Spanish Institute of Energy), Ισπανία
- ΚΑΤΕ (Κέντρο Καινοτομικών Περσών και Εξοπλισμών Ενέργειας), Ελλάδα
- FEDEAENE (European Federation of Agencies and Regions for Energy and the Environment), Βέλγιο
- ICEL (European Secretariat), Γαλλία
- Εργαστήριο de Ελέγχου, Ισπανία
- Πανεπιστήμιο Τεχνολογίας Αιολικής Ενέργειας, Ελλάδα
- Energy Agency of the 21st Region, Τσέχια
- LMA (Low Impact Mediterranean Architecture Association), Ισπανία
- Three o'clock, Γαλλία

Ακόλουθες περιοχές ("Followers")

Διαδραστικό Σχημάτιο 07.02.2024

Το πλαίσιο

Μεθοδικό πλαίσιο και τοπικές πολιτικές

- Σύμβαση Αθήνας για την Αειφόρο Ενέργεια και το Κλίμα (ΣΔΑΕ/Κ)
- Σύμβαση Ευρωπαϊκής Απόδοσης Κτιρίων
- Σύμβαση Ευρωπαϊκής Μεταβασης
- Γραμμή Ευρωπαϊκής Μεταβασης
- Παραμετρικό Σύστημα Στάθης

Μεθοδολογίες / καλές πρακτικές

Ρόλοι και δομές διακυβέρνησης

- Πλαίσιο για 30 Δήμους των Αθηνών
- Εργαστήριο Στρατηγικής Αειφόρου Κτιρίων
- Παράδειγμα Ευρωπαϊκής Μεταβασης
- Γραμμή Ευρωπαϊκής Μεταβασης
- Εργαστήριο Γραμμή Μεταβασης
- Παραμετρικό Σύστημα Στάθης
- Εθνικό Σύστημα Στάθης των Αθηνών

Υφιστάμενο δίκτυο

Διαδραστικό Σχημάτιο 07.02.2024

Κύριος στόχος

Ανάπτυξη και εφαρμογή μιας μεθοδολογίας για την ενίσχυση της πολυεπίπεδης διακυβέρνησης των δήμων αρχών και τη συντονισμένη υιοθέτηση μέτρων στην κατασκευή της ενεργειακής μετάβασης, με στόχο την επίτευξη των Ευρωπαϊκών στόχων διασφάλισης.

Διαδραστικό Σχημάτιο 07.02.2024

Πιλοτικές περιοχές

Διαδραστικό Σχημάτιο 07.02.2024

Ακόλουθες περιοχές ("Followers")

Πιλοτικές περιοχές:

- Περιφέρεια Ζίλο (Τσεχία)
- Περιφέρεια Γίτανα (Ισπανία)
- Περιφέρεια Κρήτης (Ελλάδα)

Ακόλουθες περιοχές ("Followers"):

- Αίγινα Φυλίας (Ελλάδα)
- Παραμετρικό Τμήμα Ανάπτυξης Κινητικής Αειφορίας (Ελλάδα)
- Εργαστήριο Γραμμή 3 Casettes (Γαλλία)
- Γραμμή Ευρωπαϊκής Αειφορίας και Περιβαλλοντικής Προστασίας (Φινλανδία)
- Παραμετρικό Γραμμή Μεταβασης Αειφορίας για την Ενέργεια και το Κλίμα (Βελγίους)
- Διαδικασία κίνησης Τελεφερί «Τουριστική Περιφέρεια»
- Παραμετρικό Σύστημα Στάθης (Ισπανία)

Διαδραστικό Σχημάτιο 07.02.2024

Κύριες δράσεις

Πλατφόρμα

- Τεχνητή Νοημοσύνη
- Big Data
- Σύμφωνο των Δημάρχων
- Διαδικασία
- Ψηφιοποίηση
- Μεθόδους Εκπαίδευσης
- Ευρώπη
- Δίκτυο Φόρων ενδιαφερόμενων
- Ενέργεια
- Πολυ-επίπεδη διακυβέρνηση
- Διαδραστικά σεμινάρια
- Συντονισμένη διακυβέρνηση
- Ενεργειακή Μεταβαση
- Ενδυνάμωση
- Πολιτικές περιοχές
- Εργαστήρια
- Επικοινωνιολογία
- Βιωσιμότητα
- Πολιτικές εφαρμογές
- Απονθρακοποίηση
- Αίγινα απορρίψεων

Πιλοτική φάση

- Δίκτυο που έχουν ήδη ΣΔΑΕ/Κ
- Αξιολόγηση μεθοδολογίας ePLANET για την ανταπόκριση στις ανάγκες των δήμων αρχών για την ενεργειακή μετάβαση
- Εφαρμογή της μεθοδολογίας στις πιλοτικές περιοχές (Use Cases)

Φάση μεταφοράς αποτελεσμάτων

- Λογισμικό δήμων πιλοτικών περιοχών και παραπάνω δήμοι / Περιφέρειες
- Διαδότη μεθοδολογίας σε άλλες περιοχές σε εθνικό - Ευρωπαϊκό επίπεδο
- Αναλυτική τεχνολογία

Διαδραστικό Σχημάτιο 07.02.2024

Εφαρμογή στις πιλοτικές περιοχές

Use Cases

> Γίτανα (Ισπανία), Κρήτη (Ελλάδα)

✓ Εφαρμογή (Use Case) 1 - Ψηφιοποίηση των Σχεδίων Δράσης Αειφόρου Ενέργειας και Κλίματος (ΣΔΑΕ/Κ) των Δήμων

Διευκόλυνση της διαδικασίας σύνταξης, επικαιροποίησης και παρακολούθησης των ΣΔΑΕ/Κ, μέσω της πλατφόρμας του έργου ePLANET.

Πιλοτική φάση

16 Δήμοι της Κρήτης με ΣΔΑΕ/Κ

Δελφίνος and JUST Research Centre (JRC) - Government of Aqors

Διαδραστικό Σχημάτιο 07.02.2024

Εφαρμογή στις πιλοτικές περιοχές

Use Cases

> Ζίλο (Τσεχία), Κρήτη (Ελλάδα)

✓ Εφαρμογή (Use Case) 2 - Ανάλυση ενεργειακής κατανάλωσης του δημόσιου κτιριακού αποθέματος

Διευκόλυνση της παρακολούθησης και αξιολόγησης της ενεργειακής κατανάλωσης των δήμων αρχών κτιρίων σε Δήμους, μέσω της πλατφόρμας του ePLANET.

Στοιχεία για όλους τους δήμους της Κρήτης

Διεύθυνση καταστάσεων και δίκτυο

Διαδραστικό Σχημάτιο 07.02.2024

Figure 3-18 - Crete Island activity 1 slides 1-10

Εφαρμογή στις πιλοτικές περιοχές

Use Cases ➤ [Γίρανα \(Ισπανία\), Ζίη \(Ταϊσία\), Κρήτη \(Ελλάδα\)](#)

✓ **Εφαρμογή (Use Case) 3 - Γεωχωρικά εργαλεία για την προώθηση των Ενεργειακών Κοινοτήτων**

Δημιουργία γεωχωρικού οπτικοποιημένου εργαλείου, για την υποστήριξη στο σχεδιασμό Ενεργειακών Κοινοτήτων σε τοπικό επίπεδο (με ενσωμάτωση ΑΠΕ, π.χ. Φ/Β, Βιομάζα) και την υποστήριξη προς την ενεργειακή μετάβαση, με πληροφορίες από τον κτιριακό τομέα.

Απεικόνιση σχετικών δεδομένων από την πλατφόρμα του ePLANET στην ήδη υπάρχουσα πλατφόρμα GIS της Περιφέρειας Κρήτης, με στόχο την υποστήριξη στο σχεδιασμό Ενεργειακών Κοινοτήτων

Διαδραστικό Σεμινάριο 07.02.2024

Εφαρμογή στις πιλοτικές περιοχές

Use Cases ➤ [Ζίη \(Ταϊσία\)](#)

✓ **Εφαρμογή (Use Case) 4 - Ανάλυση δυναμικού Φ/Β για δημόσια κτίρια**

Απεικόνιση, σε περιβάλλον GIS, του δυναμικού από τις εγκαταστάσεις Φωτοβολταϊκών και του βαθμού ιδιοκατανάλωσης, σε δημόσια κτίρια.

Διαδραστικό Σεμινάριο 07.02.2024

Για περισσότερες πληροφορίες

Ιστοσελίδα
<https://www.eplaneth2020.eu/el/>

Twitter
<https://twitter.com/ePlaneth2020/>

LinkedIn
<https://www.linkedin.com/company/eplaneth2020/>

YouTube
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=GW42T1Zxyg4>

Ευχαριστούμε για την προσοχή σας

www.eplaneth2020.eu

Figure 3-19 - Crete Island activity 1 slides 9-12

3.4.2 Activity 2

Πρόγραμμα Εκδήλωσης Καινοτόμα εργαλεία για την προώθηση της ενεργειακής αναβάθμισης κτιρίων με στόχο την ενεργειακή μετάβαση Παρασκευή 19 Απριλίου 2024, Ξενοδοχείο Φίλιππος (Μητσαίων 3, Αθήνα 117 42)	
09:30 – 10:00	Προσέλευση – Εγγραφές
10:00 – 10:10	Καλωσόρισμα - Χαιρετισμοί Μάρκος Δαμασιώτης, ΚΑΠΕ
10:10 – 10:25	Ολοκληρωμένες λύσεις που υποστηρίζουν τη ριζική ενεργειακή ανακαίνιση - Το Ευρωπαϊκό έργο re-MODULEES Ελπίδα Πολυχρόνη, ΚΑΠΕ
10:25 - 10:45	Ψηφιακός κόμβος ριζικής ενεργειακής ανακαίνισης – Η πλατφόρμα του έργου re-MODULEES Μαρία Μπολολιά, ΚΑΠΕ
10:45 - 11:15	Ενεργειακή αναβάθμιση κατοικιών μέσω διαδικτυακού εργαλείου Ανδρέας Ανδρουτσόπουλος, ΚΑΠΕ
11:15 – 11.45	Διάλειμμα - καφέ
11:45 – 12:00	Μοντέλο συνεργατικής διακυβέρνησης για την ενεργειακή μετάβαση – Το Ευρωπαϊκό έργο ePLANET Κατερίνα Σφακιανάκη, ΚΑΠΕ
12:00 – 12:25	Εργαλείο συλλογής ενεργειακών δεδομένων για την άμεση σύγκριση πολιτικών και μέτρων εξοικονόμησης ενέργειας μεταξύ δημόσιων αρχών – Η πλατφόρμα του έργου ePLANET Κατερίνα Σφακιανάκη, ΚΑΠΕ
12:25 – 12:40	Εμπειρία Δήμου Φυλής Χρυσούλα Κουράση, Δήμος Φυλής
12:40 – 13:00	Ολοκληρωμένα συστήματα συμμετοχικού σχεδιασμού και διαχείρισης, ως εργαλεία για την μετάβαση των Δήμων στην κλιματική ουδετερότητα Εύη Τζανακάκη, ΚΑΠΕ
13:00 – 13:15	Παραδείγματα καλών πρακτικών - Πανελλήνια Ομοσπονδία Εμπόρων & Βιοτεχνών Υαλοπινάκων (ΠΟΕΒΥ) Χρήστος Λούσης, Πρόεδρος ΔΣ
13:15 – 13:30	Παραδείγματα καλών πρακτικών - Πανελλήνιος Σύνδεσμος Διογκωμένης Πολυστερίνης (ΠΑ.ΣΥ.ΔΙ.Π.) Παντελής Πατενιώτης, Γενικός Διευθυντής
13:30 – 14:30	Κλείσιμο - Ελαφρύ γεύμα
Τα έργα συγχρηματοδοτούνται από το Πρόγραμμα Έρευνας και Καινοτομίας HORIZON 2020 της Ευρωπαϊκής Επιτροπής βάσει των υπ' αριθ. 955529 & 101032450 Συμβάσεων.	

Figure 3-20 - Crete Island agenda activity 1

ePLANET project
 European Public Local Authorities' Network for driving the Energy Transition
 Program: Horizon 2020, CSA - Coordination and support action
 Thematic: LC-SC3-EC-5-2020 - Supporting public authorities in driving the energy transition
 Duration: 3 years (01/09/2021 - 31/08/2024)
 Budget: - € 1,5 ex.

10 partners - 6 EU countries
 CIMNE (International Centre for Numerical Methods in Engineering, Spain) - Environmental studies
 ICAMN (Canadian Institute of Energy), Spain
 CREE (Εθνικό Κέντρο Έρευνας και Εφαρμογών Ενέργειας), Greece
 FESERAME (European Federation of Agencies and Regions for Energy and the Environment), Belgium
 ICLL (European Secretariat), Germany
 Instituto de Girona, Spain
 Περιφερειακό Ταμείο Ανάπτυξης Αγρίας, Ελλάδα
 Energy Agency of the Zili Region, **Local Republic**
 LIMA (Low Impact Mediterranean Architecture Association), Spain
 Three o'clock, France

ePLANET objectives
 A management and coherent transnational information sharing platform
 A data base of energy transition plans, which includes best practices and indicators of energy transition measure
 A consolidated and institutionalized ePLANET network with multi-level working groups
 A collaborative framework for the development and updating of energy transition plans.

Objectives of the Review of existing policy framework
 To undertake a review of the following aspects:
 ✓ Current legal and policy framework for energy transition in the partners' territories
 ✓ Governance status related to energy transition in current EU-wide networks and initiatives → Governance structures; Methodologies, tools, digital platforms
 ✓ Governance status related to energy transition in the 3 ePLANET pilot territories → Governance structures; Methodologies, tools, digital platforms
 ✓ Best practices on multi-level governance for energy transition, identified from past or ongoing projects of the consortium partners and beyond → Governance structures; Methodologies, tools, digital platforms
 With the following aims:
 ✓ Overview and better understanding of the current governance framework
 ✓ Identification of best practices, barriers and lessons learnt
 ✓ Feedback for ePLANET new proposed figures / structures and tools, to improve vertical and horizontal governance for energy transition

Best practices from 21 past or ongoing projects
 Review of past or ongoing, EU and national/regional projects with the participation of one or more of the consortium partners that are relevant to the ePLANET objectives
 Identification of:
 ✓ Governance structures
 ✓ Methodologies, tools, digital platforms
 that could be further exploited and linked to the new governance structures and tools to be proposed at the next stages of the ePLANET project.

Pilot Regions
 Girona Catalonia Spain
 Region of Zili Chez Republic
 Region of Crete Crete

Ακόλουθες περιοχές ("Followers")
 Πύλοτες περιοχές:
 • Περιφέρεια Ζίλη (Τσεχία)
 • Περιφέρεια Γκιρόνα (Ισπανία)
 • Περιφέρεια Αγρίας (Ελλάδα)
 Ακόλουθες περιοχές ("Followers"):
 • Δήμος Φυλίας (Ελλάδα)
 • Περιφερειακό Ταμείο Ανάπτυξης Νοτιοανατολικής Ελλάδας (Ελλάδα)
 • Ευρωπαϊκό Γραφείο 3 Γαλλίας (Γαλλία)
 • Γραφείο Ενέργειας, Αναπτυξιακό και Περιβαλλοντικό (Γαλλία)
 • Περιφερειακό Γραφείο Μείωσης εκπομπών για τον Ευρωπαϊκό Διαμέριση (Βέλγιο)
 • Αποκεντρωμένη Ενοχότητα Σάραγα-Σουά (Γαλλία)
 • Περιφερειακό Ταμείο Ανάπτυξης Λιθουανίας (Λιθουανία)

Figure 3-21 - Crete Island activity 2 slides 1-10

Εργαλείο συλλογής ενεργειακών δεδομένων για την άμεση σύγκριση πολιτικών και μέτρων εξοικονόμησης ενέργειας μεταξύ δημόσιων αρχών - Η πλατφόρμα του έργου ePLANET

EUROPEAN PUBLIC LOCAL AUTHORITIES' NETWORK FOR DRIVING THE ENERGY TRANSITION

KAPE CREES | CENTRE FOR RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCES AND SKILLS

Εφαρμογή (Use Case) 1 - Ψηφιοποίηση των Σχεδίων Δράσης Αειφόρου Ενέργειας και Κλίματος (ΣΔΑΕ/Κ) των Δήμων

Διευκόλυνση της διαδικασίας σύνταξης, επικαιροποίησης και παρακολούθησης των ΣΔΑΕ/Κ, μέσω της πλατφόρμας του έργου ePLANET.

Πιλοτική φάση
16 Δήμοι της Κρήτης με ΣΔΑΕ/Κ
Δεξιότατο και Joint Research Centre (JRC) - Government of Malta

UC1 - ΤΩΝ ΣΧΕΔΙΩΝ ΔΡΑΣΗΣ ΑΕΙΦΟΡΟΥ ΕΝΕΡΓΕΙΑΣ ΚΑΙ ΚΛΙΜΑΤΟΣ (ΣΔΑΕ/Κ) ΤΩΝ ΔΗΜΩΝ

✓ Το εργαλείο αυτό επιτρέπει στους δήμους να παρακολουθούν και να αξιολογούν τα ΣΕCΑΡ.

✓ Επιπλέον, το εργαλείο αυτό τους επιτρέπει να βλέπουν τους ενεργειακούς δείκτες, να συγκρίνουν τις ενεργειακές πληροφορίες μεταξύ των δήμων, να κάνουν κατανομές των δημοτικών καταναλώσεων, να συγκρίνουν τις δράσεις και να ανταλλάσσουν πληροφορίες

Metric	Climate 2018	2019
1. Development of Climate Action Plan	100%	100%
2. Implementation of the Plan	100%	100%
3. Implementation of Energy Efficiency Measures	100%	100%
4. Implementation of Sustainable Energy Measures	100%	100%
5. Implementation of Public Space and Green Infrastructure Measures	100%	100%
6. Implementation of Energy Efficiency Measures in Public Buildings	100%	100%
7. Implementation of Energy Efficiency Measures in Residential Buildings	100%	100%
8. Implementation of Energy Efficiency Measures in Industrial Buildings	100%	100%
9. Implementation of Energy Efficiency Measures in Transport	100%	100%
10. Implementation of Energy Efficiency Measures in Other	100%	100%

Εφαρμογή (Use Case) 2 - Ανάλυση ενεργειακής κατανάλωσης του δημόσιου κτιριακού αποθέματος

Διευκόλυνση της παρακολούθησης και αξιολόγησης της ενεργειακής κατανάλωσης των δημόσιων κτιρίων σε δήμους, μέσω της πλατφόρμας του ePLANET.

Στοιχεία για όλους τους δήμους της Κρήτης
Δείκτης αποδόσεως και ΔΕΑΕΕ

UC1 - ΤΩΝ ΣΧΕΔΙΩΝ ΔΡΑΣΗΣ ΑΕΙΦΟΡΟΥ ΕΝΕΡΓΕΙΑΣ ΚΑΙ ΚΛΙΜΑΤΟΣ (ΣΔΑΕ/Κ) ΤΩΝ ΔΗΜΩΝ

Οργανωμένη προβολή των δράσεων / ποσοστό υλοποίησης, «εγκάρσια εικόνα» του Σχεδίου Ενεργειακής Μετάβασης

Not started	Completed
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> "Eco Building" for municipal offices A training, awareness and incentive program on crop management that helps mitigate the effects of climate change on agriculture and on saving resources (energy, water, etc.) Bio-remediation of Plasson B. Fellowship Park Biological Waste Reduction Program "Charis Zero Bio-Waste" Creation and Function of a Climate Change Office 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bioclimatic Rehabilitation of Aki Paraskevi in Orea Creation of an Information Center for the Environment and Climate Change in a Municipal Building within the Municipal Garden Renovation of the Tzafalioia Square

UC2 - ΑΝΑΛΥΣΗ ΕΝΕΡΓΕΙΑΚΗΣ ΑΠΟΔΟΣΗΣ ΚΤΗΡΙΑΚΟΥ ΑΠΟΘΕΜΑΤΟΣ

Σύγκριση καταναλώσεων των κτιρίων του ίδιου Δήμου - Προτεραιοποίηση κτιρίων για ενεργειακή αναβάθμιση

UC2 - ΑΝΑΛΥΣΗ ΕΝΕΡΓΕΙΑΚΗΣ ΑΠΟΔΟΣΗΣ ΚΤΗΡΙΑΚΟΥ ΑΠΟΘΕΜΑΤΟΣ

Κάθε κτίριο - ένα λογιστικό φύλλο στο οποίο εμφανίζονται οι πληροφορίες του κτιρίου καθώς και όλα τα δεδομένα κατανάλωσης ενέργειας.

UC2 - ΑΝΑΛΥΣΗ ΕΝΕΡΓΕΙΑΚΗΣ ΑΠΟΔΟΣΗΣ ΚΤΗΡΙΑΚΟΥ ΑΠΟΘΕΜΑΤΟΣ

Ανάλυση της συνολικής κατανάλωσης ενέργειας όλων των δημοτικών κτιρίων ανά πηγή ενέργειας (ηλεκτρική ενέργεια, φυσικό αέριο, άλλα καύσιμα).

1.- CONSULT THE TOTAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION FROM THE MUNICIPALITY

Ανά πηγή ενέργειας

Ανά έτος

Figure 3-22 - Crete Island activity 2 slides 11-20

Figure 3-23 - Crete Island activity 2 slides 21-23

